

Hybrid Battery and Flywheel Energy Storage System for LEO Spacecraft

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Abstract

The use of flywheels as energy storage was probably the second thought after the wheel was invented. With the recent developments in composite materials, magnetic materials and the use of micro processors; flywheel energy storage has wide applications in many facets of our lives. For space vehicles, two counter-rotating wheels are used to produce a flywheel energy storage system (FESS). The initial flight opportunities for this flywheel technology can be used for energy storage in conjunction with existing battery and power subsystem designs. There are also possibilities that this pair of counter rotating FESS's can replace one of the attitude control wheels in the attitude control system (ACS) wheel set. This paper describes the potential combined battery/flywheel energy storage system for aerospace application. Battery charging control schemes and solar array regulation can be augmented with a flywheel system to improve spacecraft performance, allow an alternate energy storage source for single battery systems, reduce the size of the solar array and be used as one of (3 or 4) attitude control wheels.

Introduction

The flywheel has the potential to allow longer spacecraft life with reduced weight by using an alternate technology and combining the functionality of two subsystems into one. Present systems have mission life goals of 5 years and beyond. Reduced degradation of the power components is critical to continue these new mission requirements. Present batteries probably meet these current mission requirements, so do the present solar array and electronics equipment. A flywheel energy storage system (FESS) in conjunction with a chemical energy storage has potential to extend mission life, reduce spacecraft weight and use as one of the ACS wheels in a spacecraft configurations. FESS has additional benefits in manufacturing and during spacecraft I&T. The energy available can be determined by looking at the speed and there will be no need for a work horse FESS and to store the of flight FESS. Manufacturing and process controls are different for flywheels than chemical batteries. FESS development offers manufacturing with different process constraints that may lead to alternate system and integration approaches.

The present spacecraft designs whether direct energy transfer (DET) or peak power tracker (PPT), both use solar arrays for energy conversion of solar energy to electrical energy. This energy must be controlled, generally to a battery dominated bus (unregulated or regulated) voltage. Existing systems either DET's or PPT's, battery dominated or regulated voltage buses all need to perform battery charging. Low earth orbit spacecraft generally have eclipse about every 100 minutes and these eclipse generally last about 30 minutes. A cold solar array can generate its maximum power after it comes from the eclipse. This power is needed to provide continuous power to the spacecraft load and charge the batteries. Present electrochemical systems start the charge at a constant current with temperature-compensated voltage clamp, a taper to a lower charge rate and then to a trickle charge. Consistent and prolonged interruptions during this charge may reduce battery performance and/or battery life. The end of charge taper and trickle regimes do not require the full solar array output capability. Therefore, solar array regulation schemes deal with this excess power either by shunting it or by leaving

it on the array. In addition the peak load demands may undercharge the battery. A FESS operating in conjunction with a battery can augment the battery charge rates, use the wasted array power and allow battery charging without peak load interruptions. Also, a FESS can augment the battery discharge to insure longer life and provide additional redundancy.

NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (NASA/GSFC) is vigorously researching many forms and types of flywheels that have potential aerospace and commercial application. GSFC has been developing both FESS and Integrated Power and Attitude Control Systems (IPACS) since the early 1960's.

Concept

NASA Lewis Research Center (NASA/LeRC) has a 1000 watt hour FESS development program jointly with U.S. Flywheel Systems and TRW. And, Eagle Picher has 50 Ah single pressure vessel (SPV) in production for the Iridium program. This paper identifies the potential of these two energy storage systems together and describes the system concept and benefits. At NASA/GSFC several independent study teams have studied such a configuration. The Integrated Mission Design Center (IMDC) at NASA/GSFC is also interested and has studied several viable application for such a system. Plans for a integrating this concept into a future spacecraft are being discussed along with possible routes for technology transfer to commercial aerospace vendors and to terrestrial applications.

The Typical charge discharge profile for a SPV is shown in the following figure.

During the constant current charge, the current vs time is shown as a flat portion of the figure, consequently the cell voltage ramps up. In a spacecraft this constant current is derived by the strings of solar cells. In the beginning of

mission life the solar array converts more power than required and the unneeded segments are either shunted or left open circuited. Solar arrays near the end of life has a reduced power capability which may not be able to provide this flat constant current profile, consequently the battery charge rate, battery performance and life may be at risk. After the constant current charge, there is a taper charge followed by a trickle charge as the battery reached full state of charge. During this period the spacecraft would be shunting solar array energy. The solar array energy that is not used during this portion of the charge can be made available for storage into a FESS with no increase to the size of the solar array. The FESS energy can be discharged to the bus during the eclipse period reducing the battery depth of discharge and allowing the battery to have a longer life. The FESS can also be available to provide peak power during the discharge cycle.

A FESS can be beneficial to a traditional battery system by tailoring optimum charge and discharge profiles for a particular cell/battery characteristics. The spacecraft solar array can be reduced. Furthermore battery reconditioning is possible when required. A counter rotating pair of flywheel will be used for energy storage and possibly as one of the attitude control wheels in a set of either 3 or 4 wheels. The wheel will store and supply power to the bus, as needed to insure beneficial characteristics for the battery. The battery charge profile normally do not exceed C/2 charge rate, however higher charge rates and longer tapered charge rates can be available during an anomalous cell/battery conditions. Discharge at a constant loads are also achievable. Generally the depth of discharge (DOD) can be reduced and discharge profiles can be controlled. Battery thermal concerns can be elevated by decreasing the battery load if temperature set points have been exceeded. ACS actuation's can also be accomplished by transferring energy from one wheel to the other, allowing both wheels to spin down or spinning the wheel up.

Basic Equations:

Available energy is given as:

$$SED = KE/M$$

SED = Specific Energy Density
KE = Kinetic Energy

M= Rotor Mass in Kg.

$$K_e = j \omega^2 / 2$$

j = Rotor mass moment of inertia (Kg*m²)

ω = Angular Velocity (rad/sec)

A FESS stores energy in the rotation of the rotor. The energy stored is directly related to the rotor speed. The following is an example rotor.

University of Maryland Rotor info

OD .1676m, ID .1067m, h .2286m

Weight was 5.67kg

Volume was .0003m³

Density 1.89 X 10³ kg/m³

Rotor Density

Graphite D=1.89 10³ kg/m³

Rotor Volume

$$V = \pi h r_o^2 - \pi h r_i^2$$

$$V = .007m^3$$

The following is an exercise of sizing a flywheel for a 1 kilo-watt-hour application. The rotor dimensions have an impact on the energy storage capability along with the speed. In this example the system is cycled from 2,333 RPM to 7,000 RPM and delivering 1 Kwh of energy.

The weight of the system are assumed based on components from University of Maryland and Fare Inc. information along with an estimate of the rotor mass.

System Weight Estimate
for Graphite Epoxy Rotor

Item	(kg)
96102 BGB weight estimate	
Mag Bearing 2.5# x 2 each	2.273
Motor/Generator	.909
Mag Bearing Controller	1.364
Motor/Generator Controller	1.364
Enclosure	2.273
Rotor	12.797
Total	20.98

The maximum specific energy density (SED) is dependent on the type of rotor material and process used to manufacture the rotor. Qualification for the rotor is being looked at. One way would be to burst a sibling rotor and use a derating factor for the maximum operating speed. Another alternative being discussed is to monitor the health of the system and provide a controlled shutdown.

Rotor Configuration

$$h = .3048 \text{ m}$$

$$ID = .1905 \text{ m}$$

$$r_i = ID/2$$

$$r_i = .095m$$

$$OD = .2540$$

$$r_o = OD/2$$

$$r_o = 0.127m$$

Rotor Speed

$$f_2 = 70000 \text{ RPM}$$

$$f_1 = f_2/3.00$$

$$v = 2 \pi f_1$$

$$w = 2 \pi f_2$$

$$f_1 = 388.889 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

$$v = 2.443 \cdot 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

$$w = 7.33 \cdot 10^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$$

Energy Storage

$$I = (m [r_i^2 + r_o^2]) / 2$$

$$K_e = (I [w^2 - v^2]) / 2$$

$$K_e = 3.843 \cdot 10^6 \text{ sec watt}$$

$$Wh = K_e / 3600 \text{ sec/hr}$$

$$SED_1 = wh/m$$

$$SED_1 = 83.592 \text{ watt hr/kg}$$

$$I = 0.161 \text{ kg m}^2$$

$$Wh = 1.068 \cdot 10^3 \text{ watt hr}$$

Implementation

We at NASA GSFC propose to use the 1000 wh, 22.727 kg FESS in a counter rotating pair for future missions. Several good prospects have already been identified working in conjunction

with the Integrated Mission Design Center (IMDC). In order to continue the development of this approach an implementation plan has been proposed.

The Space Power Applications Branch would like to use it's Power System Testbed for conversion to an IPACS Testbed. The testbed has a capability up to 2 kilowatt and is presently configured for 120 volt DC power bus. This testbed can be modified to provide bus voltages from 28 volts DC to 120 volts DC. It was built by Virginia Tech in Blacksberg VA for NASA/GSFC. The original purpose of the Testbed was to prove out several concepts for the 120 volt DC power bus. The system served it's purpose very well. We now propose to recycle this test bed for flywheel applications. Thus, we can get dual use of the system. The test bed uses a solar array simulator with brass board spacecraft functional components for solar array regulation, mode control, battery charging , battery discharging. An alternate bi-directional battery charger/discharge is also available. Battery simulators and dynamic load simulators are also available. System features and different configurations are programmable. The system offers simulation of a many power system functions for shunt mode, charge mode and discharge mode operation and stability research.

Proposed second phase plans are to augment the Power System Testbed with magnetic bearing control equipment and a flywheel test safety enclosure to provide spacecraft FESS test capability. At this phase of the IPACS Testbed development, the planned FESS described in this paper will be tested under spacecraft operating conditions for a selected mission. In addition, via NASA/GSFC Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) with DOE, technology transfer from space development to terrestrial and automobile applications can be assessed with operational data.

A proposed third phase would be to add attitude control system (ACS) features to the Testbed and complete the development for the IPACS Testbed. The IPACS testbed will explore operation of the flywheel devices for both EPS and ACS. It will be a platform for testing alternate magnetic gearing controllers, motor-generators and software control schemes.

Conclusions

This concept of operating a FESS with a battery is a natural evolution to introduce the concept of using flywheels for energy storage and to explore the benefits for optimizing battery management. Information and data from this study could reduced the of weight of spacecraft and the solar array size.